

Spiritual self-consciousness, an Approach to Reduce the Suffering of the Contemporary Human

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Abstract

In the modern world, contemporary humans are faced with diverse challenges, sometimes leading to feelings of tension, hopelessness, and suffering. While rapid social, economic, and technological developments facilitate life, they may also bring about feelings such as loneliness, disorientation, and other types of suffering. This is mostly explained based on extreme attachment to the world of matter and tangible items and failure to believe in the invisible world, the metamaterial, and metaphysical concepts. Those who experience such a state undergo a fundamental crisis in terms of their spiritual system and, hence, feel distressed and need spiritual counseling. In the meantime, the concept of spiritual self-consciousness is presented as a way to cope with the above forms of suffering and maintain balance in one's life. Self-consciousness has various types: 1. Physical self-consciousness, 2. Mental self-consciousness, 3. Social self-consciousness, and 4. Spiritual self-consciousness. Spiritual self-consciousness refers to attaining a profound understanding of oneself, getting connected to the world, and seeking meaning in one's life. Spiritual spheres play an important role in the process of discovering spiritual self-consciousness. Spiritual spheres refer to specific situations or circumstances that typically provide the necessary context for the occurrence of spiritual experiences in humans. The present study aimed to analyze the concept of spiritual self-consciousness and discover its actualization process and impacts on the lives of contemporary humans. In the present study, which was carried out using library citation and descriptive-analytical techniques, it was shown that spiritual self-consciousness is formed according to spiritual spheres and emotions. Based on the Quranic verses and Hadiths, there are at least four types of spiritual spheres, including prayer, creation, one's nature, and plights. Humans who face each one of the above become prone to perceive various spiritual spheres and face God's representations, resulting in the attainment of spiritual self-consciousness. Equipped with this form of self-consciousness, contemporary humans deal with the challenges in their lives in a more intelligent and in-depth manner. Moreover, they assign meaning to their suffering and move toward mental and emotional well-being.

Keywords: Self-consciousness, Spiritual self-consciousness, Contemporary human, Function of spirituality, Spiritual experience

Introduction

In human beings, there is a profound need to transcend and get connected to forces above the material world, and this is represented in religion and spirituality [1]. Spirituality in humans can appear in the form of spiritual experiences as Islam considers humans as creatures who seek divinity according to their very nature (ar-Rum, 30). Thus, if human beings contemplate their transcendental needs and explore the depths of their souls, they will clearly see the divine light and faith in monotheism, which is already bestowed upon them (al-A'raf, 172) [2]. Spiritual emotions and humans' innate tendency toward matters like their desire to learn and know the world of existence, interest in absolute power and perfection, and inclination toward beauty all originate from God, and consciousness about the existence of such intrinsic inclinations in humans guide them toward their origins, which are called divine features [3]. Based on this, God cannot be ignored in the definition of spirituality as some researchers have called spirituality a kind of unlimited mental capacity that is actualized through establishing a relationship with the Creator [4]. However, it can be argued that, according to Islam, spiritual emotions and experiences that take place in spheres like existence in creation, plights, praying, and facing oneself are all connected to God, though the experiencers may take no notice of the entity their experience pertains to, i.e., God [5].

The concept of self-consciousness

Self-consciousness is the ability to pay attention to oneself and one's diverse features. Using the skill, individuals examine themselves as observers and process their personal information. Self-consciousness is the ability to observe oneself [6]. Based on this ability, people can take notice of their feelings and thoughts during daily activities and become aware of their effects on their decisions and actions. For instance, when you listen to one of your friends complaining about their work, you may feel some tension and contraction in your body, criticize your friend, think about some guidance and advice, and become aggrieved by their unhappiness. Such reactions mean you care for others' unhappiness, listen to them, and are sensitive to their problems. Knowing all of the above suffices to equip you with mental self-consciousness. Thus, the above example shows that self-consciousness enables people to know their feelings, motives, states, logical and illogical conditions, and other behaviors and become aware of them. It is obvious that such awareness makes people less prone to impulsive and illogical decisions.

Types of self-consciousness

As the self consists of various dimensions, including physical, mental, social, and spiritual, there is no doubt that self-consciousness itself can be divided into the following dimensions: 1. Physical self-consciousness, 2. Mental self-consciousness, 3. Social self-consciousness, and 4. Spiritual self-consciousness [7].

The significance of spirituality in self-consciousness

It is noteworthy that spiritual self-consciousness is considerably more important than other types of self-consciousness as it influences other aspects. A person who has strong and special religious and spiritual beliefs is different from people less concerned with spiritual dimensions in terms of personality and behavioral dimensions. That is because spirituality has in-depth, extensive, and fundamental impacts on humans, and differences among people in that regard would lead to much more fundamental differences. A question that arises here is how differences between individuals in terms of spiritual characteristics result in remarkable differences among them in terms of mental and social characteristics. As there are considerably important and decisive matters in spiritual self-consciousness, including moral values and standards or belief in God and the hereafter, it is obvious that such differences would also influence other existential aspects in humans. For instance, consider an individual who has set high moral standards for themselves. It is clear that such moral standards will significantly influence the person's beliefs, actions, and activities in the personal, familial, and social spheres. Imagine another person who believes in excellent human values like trustworthiness, loyalty, and truthfulness. Similarly, it seems obvious that the values the person believes in will influence their thinking, actions, and activities across personal and social areas. If such people have a good command of the above characteristics, how will they define themselves? What are their criteria for assessing their worth? What do they do during hardships? How likely are they to be involved in risky and unhealthy activities? How do they view hardships and suffering in life? What are their habits? What are their joys? What does their entertainment look like? How do they express negative emotions? What behaviors are less frequent in them? How do they experience positive feelings and emotions? How do people who do not abide by excellent human values react to the above questions? As can be seen, humans' spiritual dimensions significantly influence other aspects of their lives. Thus, it is important for them to become aware of the spiritual dimensions and get the best of them.

Spiritual self-consciousness

Spiritual self-consciousness is one of the most significant topics discussed in self-consciousness and involves knowing one's spiritual dimensions and becoming conscious and aware of them. As discussed before, humans are creatures with biological, mental, social, and spiritual dimensions. However, spiritual matters and their significance in life have been typically ignored. There are highly important topics in self-consciousness, including one's religion and religious beliefs, moral values and standards, the meaning of life, one's purpose in life, believing in God, and believing in

the hereafter. As a useful skill, self-consciousness helps people to make good use of their personal capabilities and skills. In other words, people with weak self-consciousness will fail to make efficient use of their capabilities and skills, including their spiritual potential.

Understanding spiritual experiences and, hence, one's spiritual aspects requires a skill called spiritual self-consciousness. Spiritual self-consciousness refers to people's ability to accurately know their feelings, emotions, and characteristics in a way that they understand the reason underlying a certain emotion and are informed about the reason and manner of excitement across various situations [8]. When this type of self-consciousness is applied to a spiritual context and the origin of the created emotions becomes clear, spiritual self-consciousness is formed. In this way, spiritual self-consciousness can be considered as paying attention to one's state facing various frequent experiences where humans encounter God. Hence, they accurately perceive the emotions formed through such experiences and become aware of the spiritual dimensions of that encounter. Some psychologists have applied spiritual self-consciousness and religious teachings in psychotherapy and counseling. In other words, they have tried to facilitate their patients' spiritual identification by discovering and assessing their spirituality [9].

After defining the religious experience as exposure to the Divine Being, another question arises: Whether people can attain the religious experience using scientific methods? The answer is absolutely positive. Indeed, the real religious experience can be facilitated by incorporating certain aspects of reality, focusing on a series of understandable and perceptual matters, and acknowledging people's potential to enjoy experiences taught by religions [10]. The above argument clearly indicates the role of spiritual self-consciousness in facilitating the perception of spiritual and religious experiences.

Religious spheres play an important role in discovering spiritual self-consciousness. Spiritual spheres refer to certain conditions and circumstances that create the context for the occurrence of spiritual experiences in humans. Researchers have specified various spiritual spheres based on their understanding of spirituality. Preston and Shin (2016) categorized eight types of spiritual experiences, including religious experiences, life and death experiences like the birth of a child or the death of loved ones, experiences related to nature, connection to others, culmination experiences, and meditation [11]. Moreover, Greely (1975) pointed to various factors like music, prayer, natural beauties, silent contemplation, taking part in church services, and listening to sermons [12].

Spiritual self-consciousness is formed according to spiritual spheres and emotions. Spiritual spheres and emotions refer to areas perceived during the occurrence of a spiritual experience, resulting in the formation of the corresponding spiritual self-consciousness. According to Pargament, if we stand on the edge of a rock and look down at a scene in the Grand Canyon, it would be surprising if we experience feelings like wonder, amazement, astonishment, and even a mixture of happiness and gratefulness [13]. Thus, spiritual spheres and emotions are among the components that make up spiritual self-consciousness.

So far, scholars have proposed various spiritual models. Poll and Smith (2003) proposed a spiritual model based on the assumptions of Divinity, including pre-consciousness, awakening, recognition, and integration. In the model, individuals are driven toward the opportunities of having spiritual experiences in a way that they can recognize their spiritual nature and begin connecting to God and others under certain terms and conditions [14]. Janbozorgi argued that humans' perceptual arena consisted of four main topics, including the origin, the hereafter, existence, and the self, founding his multidimensional method of spiritual psychotherapy on the regulation of that perceptual arena. His therapeutic method includes a theoretical anthropological framework based on which, a general principle is extracted as the main core [15].

The components of spiritual self-consciousness

Spiritual experiences do not take place in a vacuum; rather, they require the establishment of a context to nurture the experience. According to the Quranic verses and Hadiths, there are at least four spiritual spheres, including prayer, creation, one's nature, and plights. When humans face the

above spheres, they get ready to perceive various spiritual spheres and encounter Divine manifestations, leading to the establishment of spiritual self-consciousness. The holy Quran and Hadiths frequently emphasize the instances of spiritual spheres and recommend humans to experience and face them. Frequent reference in the Holy Quran to various creation phenomena [16], encouraging humans to pray [17], and focusing on one's special state during plights [18] are all instances of emphasizing spiritual self-consciousness. In the Al-Tawhid Hadith narrated by Sheykh Al-Saduq, the Imam uses mental visualization and asks the narrator to imagine facing one of the spheres leading to spiritual experiences (i.e., plights). Imagining oneself on the board of a broken ship in the middle of a storm brings about such context. In Verse 19 of al-Mulk, humans are called to face another sphere involved in the formation of spiritual experiences (creation) by looking at their own existence ("Have they not seen the birds above them, spreading and folding their wings?"). The Holy Quran is an objective-oriented book that invites humans to observe experientially and judicially and regards observing as the precursor to contemplation and perceptiveness [19]. In a serious manner, the Quranic verses and Hadiths deal with the topic of creation and invite humans to observe and experience it. According to Islam, creation is the manifestation of God as He is manifested to humans through His creation [20].

A lot of verses in the Holy Quran invite humans to contemplate themselves. In other words, thinking about one's own nature makes up a major theme in the verses revolving around creation. Facing oneself, the manner by which humans are born and die, and the way they live bring about special in-depth spiritual self-consciousness. Once, humans were nonexistent (al-Insan: 1), then, they were surprisingly (ar-Rum: 54) born as conscious creatures (al-Insan: 2) from a drop of water (an-Nahl: 4) in utter weakness (ar-Rum: 54). Then, they gradually gained strength (ar-Rum: 54), though, ultimately, they became weak again (ar-Rum: 54), left the world, and entered another one extending for eternity (al-Hud: 160, 107). A lot of verses and Hadiths have paid in-depth attention to each of the above stages, making humans aware of them. Different manifestations of humans' self-consciousness and the emotions that may arise following the attention to the above evolutionary process can bring about spiritual self-consciousness.

The function of spiritual self-consciousness in the contemporary world

Spirituality is a basic need of modern human beings, acting as a requirement to give direction and meaning to every aspect of them. Without spirituality, humans are like a ship with no wheel and anchor, sailing on a turbulent sea. There is neither a destination nor a clear route, with the waves moving the ship in every direction. Contemporary human beings need spirituality for a plethora of reasons, including the need to have meaning in life, the need to be safe and secure against dangers, the need to get connected to God and experience the connection, the need to give and receive true love, the need to have calmness and acceptance, the need to achieve healing and tranquility during hardships and losses, and the need to feel worthy and in command of one's own fate - among others. As it can be observed above, contemporary humans who lack spirituality cannot assign meaning to their lives and the hardships they suffer. Without spirituality, neither the feeling of security nor tranquility and the acceptance of hardships in life will be meaningless. Spirituality gives security, tranquility, meaning, and direction to one's life. When spirituality gets weak or people's meaning frameworks and value/belief systems become distorted, negative mental states emerge that are typically manifested in the following manner: crying, guilt, the loss of trust, feeling detachment from God, extreme-to-average anxiety, and anger and fury toward others. All of the above are forms of false suffering originating from their materialistic worldviews, attachment to worldly matters and appearances, comparing what one has and does not have, and believing in the assumption that there is nothing beyond this ephemeral world and its materialistic joys. This is the very false suffering and grief that afflicts contemporary humans. Those who experience such states are undergoing fundamental crises in their spiritual systems. Thus, they suffer from distress and need immediate spiritual and meaning-oriented counseling. A question may arise here: What is the function of spirituality in one's life so much so that its collapse brings about such distress?

Becoming aware of the functions of spirituality or spiritual self-consciousness has in-depth and extensive impacts on humans' lives, and all of such functions can be considered gifts to reduce the suffering of contemporary humans. Most of such suffering is not real but false and appearance as it generally arises due to extreme devotion to materialism and the lack of belief in metaphysics and the metamaterial.

The functions of spirituality can be summarized as follows: 1. Creating meaning in life, 2. Establishing a purpose and goal in life, 3. Respecting humans' status and place, 4. Creating hope and positive feelings, 5. Improving and promoting coping strategies in individuals, and 6. Increasing positive social interactions.

1. Creating meaning in life

The suffering of contemporary humans arises due to their attachment to matter and whatever is material. In other words, as they view nothing other than the matter in their worldview, they become limited and bounded by materialism and ephemeral worldly pleasures. Meaning is the non-material reality with which humans explain their existence in the world. Having meaning in life can bring about lots of positive functions, including satisfaction with one's life, enjoying work, happiness, and positive emotions and feelings like hope. Moreover, having meaning in life brings about in-depth physical health and well-being. As there is more meaning in life, the rate of mental issues and illnesses reduces proportionately. Moreover, there is a positive relationship between having meaning in life and reducing mental and social issues like suicide and substance abuse. It is very important to note that spiritual people experience more purposefulness, efficiency, self-worth, and self-valuation according to how they view their lives and how they establish social and interpersonal relationships.

2. Establishing a purpose and goal in one's life

Spiritual beliefs help contemporary humans to know that their lives and whatever takes place in them are not without meaning and purpose, but they have causes and purposes. Accepting this in one's life, particularly during hardships, makes it much easier to cope with difficulties. That is because such people believe there is a certain purpose and end in their lives, above anything that is materialistic. The suffering of contemporary humans originates from their attachment to matter and material entities as they see themselves as limited and bounded by material entities and ephemeral worldly pleasures.

3. Respecting humans' status and position

People with spiritual beliefs regard human beings very highly and respect each human in a remarkable manner. In non-materialistic and spiritual viewpoints, people's status is not a function of their position, education, beauty, or wealth. As humans' worth according to such views does not arise from any external factor, they see it illogical to become anxious for no reason, see themselves entangled in false suffering, and feel worried about losing their status and position. That is because they always feel worthy. The ultimate result is that spiritual people feel profound tranquility and are free from modern false suffering. Thus, such people experience high self-esteem, and it is obvious that such people, even when they face real suffering and hardships in life, feel less hurt and act better in terms of coping with difficult circumstances. Spiritual teachings create an atmosphere of kindness, respect, care, empathy, and care for humans in the modern age. It is clear that having such characteristics and, most importantly, becoming aware of and applying them in one's life will be remarkably helpful in increasing social support in times of exposure to false suffering, crisis, and anxiety.

4. Establishing hope and positive feelings

Spiritual beliefs can bring about a lot of positive feelings and emotions, including hope. Spiritual people believe in the influence of a higher force over humans' lives, controlling every matter at hand. Thus, they entrust that higher force to perform whatever they do in their lives. In other words, they hope to achieve whatever they desire and stay away from anything they consider unfavorable.

The existence of positive feelings, including hope, plays a remarkable role in increasing contemporary humans' mental health and the reduction of their suffering.

5. Improving and promoting coping strategies

Being aware of the existence of spiritual views and positive and meaningful attitudes toward incidents and crises in life and implementing them in a timely manner promotes coping strategies and the quality of them. Moreover, when faced with internal and external suffering, it enables people to actively cope with their issues and problems instead of acting in a distressed and passive manner.

Conclusion

Self-consciousness is the ability to observe oneself concerning one's feelings and thoughts and includes physical, mental, social, and spiritual self-consciousness. In addition to increasing self-control and the power to manage one's emotions, self-consciousness helps people to make accurate decisions in their lives. A factor that significantly influences people's personality aspects and traits is spiritual self-consciousness. That is because spirituality has lots of influential functions in people's lives like creating meaning in life, establishing a purpose and end for one's life, respecting humans' status and position, creating hope and positive feelings, and improving and promoting coping skills. Based on what went before, it can be understood that failure to understand spiritual self-consciousness is the main crisis entangling humans in the contemporary world. Due to this shortcoming, contemporary humans apparently face a lot of suffering. However, most of that is in the form of false suffering that mostly arises due to extreme attachment to material and tangible entities and failure to believe in the metamaterial and metaphysical concepts and, most importantly, their failure to choose an accurate worldview. Spiritual self-consciousness is formed according to spiritual spheres and emotions. Spiritual spheres and emotions refer to those spheres that are perceived during the occurrence of spiritual experiences, leading to the formation of corresponding spiritual self-consciousness. Based on the Quranic verses and Hadiths, there are at least four spiritual spheres, including prayer, creation, one's nature, and plights. People who face one of the above become prepared to perceive various spiritual spheres and encounter Divine Manifestations, resulting in the formation of spiritual self-consciousness. Self-consciousness is made up of four stages, proceeding from a lack of awareness toward contemplation and full consciousness. As people continue their journeys on the path toward self-consciousness and become more self-conscious, they tend to focus more on other forces above and beyond humans. When their self-consciousness increases and they focus more on spiritual states, mental well-being gets promoted. As a result, contemporary humans' quality of life and positive emotions increase, and, at the same time, their suffering gets reduced.

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